

EDITORIAL

What is Plagiarism?

A publication in a reputed journal is the best recognition an academicians gets for his academic aptitude. But stealing someone's work and presenting to the world as your own is Plagiarism. There are mainly six types of plagiarism.

Complete / Global plagiarism: Stealing someone's research work, copying it and representing it as your own. This comes under the most serious categories of plagiarism. Doing this you will be blacklisted by most of the indexed journals.

Paraphrase plagiarism: Rephrasing a piece of text, sentence or paragraph into your own words and publishing it as your own is called paraphrasing. This plagiarism is most prevalent of all the other type of plagiarism.

Verbatim / Copy and Paste plagiarism: Copying the work of other researchers and pasting in your manuscript without any citations and quotations, making them look as your original creation. Again, this falls under serious category of plagiarism. A good plagiarism checking software will easily detect this type of plagiarism.

Mosaic / Patchwork plagiarism: When we copy thoughts and ideas from different sources and assemble them together to form a new text and representing it as your own original manuscript. This is most common with review articles.

Self-plagiarism: Republishing part of your own work which had been previously published.

Accidental plagiarism: This happens due to ignorance and unintentional when you forget to cite or quote the source article.

Hence every student, researcher and scholar should avoid these types of malpractices to enrich the academic world and get your hard work published in a decorated publication.

I conclude by saying that I take great pleasure to present you the second issue of the second volume of "**Journal of Orofacial Rehabilitation**", the official publication of Indian Prosthodontic Society West Bengal State Branch on this auspicious day of 15th August 2022 when the nation celebrates the 75th year of independence or "**AMRIT MAHOTSAV**". This is the year Indian Prosthodontic Society celebrates its 50th year or "**The Golden Jubilee**". My heartfelt regards to all authors for their hard work and contribution. I sincerely thank all our office bearers, editorial board members, and branch members for guiding and supporting me in bring out this publication.

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Editor-in-Chief

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